

THE BRITISH INSTITUTE OF PERSIAN STUDIES

مؤسسه ایرانشناسی بریتانیا

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17th October, 1971.

Dear Andrew,

I am sending this note down with Dick Forge. I am glad to hear that your work has gone well, without any difficulties. Well done -

Naimi was not helpful when I went to see him so if nothing got through to you from me in August that is now perhaps for the best. But at the same time I apologize for the fact that no direct news reached you from me - ^(I am sure I sent some news via the post, but I am not certain how things went wrong.)

When David W. was here I took up the question of fieldwork in the south with H. E. and he told me that it looked as if amicable solutions were still not clear, and for this reason he said that it would be

best if none of us continued to do any
fieldwork there once the celebrations were
over. In other words, please only work
in Shiraz from now on until you come
up to Tehran - and, as we all hope, the 'air clears'.

I shall leave for London on or about
the 24th of October and will be back again
sometime after mid-December.

If you have time to let me know of
your more immediate plans - writing
here or ~~to~~^{to} the Academy in London that
would be very nice -

Yours ever,

David.

P.S. I was shown some pots at the Museum Durson
room - after Durson - and they said that you
had said that I would collect them? I was
a bit mystified.

D.